

THE EFFECTS OF HYGROTHERMAL AGEING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Conventional composites used in structural applications are generally relying on petroleum based synthetic materials that are energy intensive to produce, expensive, and difficult to recycle. Recently, new environmentally considerate materials have been explored and introduced to alleviate environmental concern and address societal awareness. However, the variability of natural constituent materials leads to varying performance and compatibility issues between fibres and resin. As the resin has been reported to as having a greater environmental impact [1] and little data exists on resin performance, the research reported herein seeks to determine the viability of using glass fibre reinforcement with linseed oil resin for structural applications in wet, humid environments through monitoring changes in mechanical properties after moisture absorption.

Exposing composite materials to a humid environment leads to complex internal processes, which tend to degrade the material's mechanical properties. Therefore, it is important to understand which material parameters control the process of water absorption and degradation of properties.

Several researchers have investigated the hygrothermal ageing of composites. Loos and Springer [2] looked at ageing of glass/polyester composites in distilled and salt water at 23 and 50°C. They found that in distilled water the equilibrium moisture content was 3.5% and was temperature independent. In salt water however, the higher temperature caused an increase in moisture content after the initial equilibrium condition. The moisture uptake at 23 °C quoted at approximately 1% is similar to that observed by other researchers ([3], [4]). Adams and Singh [5] and Kootsookos and Mouritz [3] found that moisture uptake of

composites depends also on the reinforcement. Glass fibre reinforced composites were found to absorb more moisture than carbon fibre reinforced composites. Nogueira *et al.* [6] showed the dependence of moisture absorption on the resin curing cycle. Thomason [7] demonstrated that moisture uptake of glass/epoxy composites may vary from 2% to 7.5% for a composite with void contents of 0.8% to 3.51% respectively. Adams and Singh [5] found that in salt water the flexural modulus of glass/epoxy specimens reduced by approximately 25%. However, Gellert and Turley [4] found 17% reduction in flexural strength and only 5% reduction in flexural modulus of glass/polyester composites.

Iglesias *et al.* [8] investigated the effect of fibre coating on moisture absorption and degradation of properties of glass/epoxy composites in distilled water. They found that after ageing the properties were the same for all the specimens, indicating that the significant degradation of the interface region was independent of the coating.

To date the moisture absorption and ageing of plant oil based resins has not been widely investigated. Andjelkovic *et al.* [9] present chemical, physical, thermal and mechanical properties of several plant oil based resins including linseed oil. While they do provide mechanical properties of these resins (Young's modulus of linseed oil based resin 99.9 MPa and ultimate strength 5.6 MPa), there is no indication of the effects of ageing. Sharma and Kundu [10] also reviewed different vegetable oil based resins, but with regard to linseed oil resin they only reviewed its chemical properties. Pfister and Larock [11] present mechanical properties and moisture uptake of linseed oil-based composite reinforced with wheat straw. Their research however gives little insight into the performance of linseed oil resin as the wheat straw reinforcement had a greater impact on the moisture absorption and tested

mechanical properties. Lazko *et al.* [12] investigated the effect of linseed oil resin on the moisture absorption properties of flax fibres. Adding the resin to the fibres decreased water absorption and improved the performance of the fibres. However, the properties of the resin were not the main interest of the research. The hygrothermal ageing of glass/linseed oil composites has not yet been reported in the scientific community.

In this research a materials test programme has been undertaken which encompasses the issues of environmental degradation and durability of composite materials in a humid environment. The effect of water diffusion on the flexural properties and flexural failure modes of glass reinforced linseed oil resin in comparison with epoxy resin has been investigated.

2 Experimental Details

2.1 Material Preparation

Glass/epoxy specimens were prepared by resin infusion using 10 layers of 210g/m^2 $0^\circ/90^\circ$ plain weave glass fibre fabric RE210D by Gurit SPTTM as reinforcement. A laminate thickness of 2mm was required. The epoxy resin used was PrimeTM 20LV manufactured by Gurit SPTTM. The laminate was cured for 24 hours at ambient temperature and post-cured at 50°C for 16 hours (recommended by the manufacturer).

Glass/linseed oil specimens were prepared by hand lay-up and UV-cure using the same reinforcement. The glass/linseed oil laminates were manufactured by Sustainable Composites Ltd.

Fibre volume fraction was calculated for both materials according to ASTM D 3171. The average fibre volume fraction of glass/epoxy specimens was 48% and glass/linseed oil specimens 29%.

2.2 Moisture Uptake

The moisture uptake testing was carried out in accordance with ASTM D 5229/D 5229M standard. Specimens with nominal dimensions of $100 \times 100\text{mm}$ were first dried in an oven at 35°C and then immersed in distilled water at 40°C to accelerate the ageing process (hygrothermal ageing). The edges of the specimens were sealed with microcrystalline wax in order to assure water ingress only in the through-thickness direction. After immersing the specimens, they were weighed on a weekly basis

with a scale Mettler PE3600 with readability of $\pm 0.01\text{ g}$. For the first 2 weeks of immersion the weighing was carried out twice a week. The specimens were dried with an absorbent lint-free cloth prior to weighing. For each weighing, the specimens were out of the water bath for approximately 7 minutes.

2.3 Flexural Properties

The flexural properties testing was carried out in accordance with the test standard ASTM D 7264/D 7264M. Specimens for flexural testing were cut from $300 \times 100\text{mm}$ panels. The ageing procedure is described in Section 2.2. The support span used was $20h$ (where h is the thickness of the specimen). The width and length of glass/epoxy specimens were 50mm and 13mm, for glass/linseed oil the same parameters were 70 and 13mm. 5 specimens were tested from each set with 2 week intervals to gain flexural strength and moduli as a function of hygrothermal ageing time. Tests were carried out with electromechanical testing machine Instron 5569. Crosshead displacement was 1mm/min and flexural modulus was calculated using the crosshead displacement.

2.4 X-ray Computed Tomography

X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) was used to detect differences in failure modes of the specimens. The imaging was performed using a benchtop Nikon/Metrix CT 160Xi scanner. Data for epoxy/glass specimens were collected at 70 kV and $117\ \mu\text{A}$ with magnification of 5.47; data for linseed oil/glass specimens were collected at 80 kV and $90\ \mu\text{A}$ with magnification of 5.27.

For the reconstruction of data, CT images were acquired from 1900 rotation views over 360° of rotation. Reconstruction was performed using CT-Pro 3D software by Nikon Metrology, Inc.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Moisture Uptake

Figure 1 shows moisture uptake curves for glass/epoxy and glass/linseed oil specimens over an 18 week period. By the end of this test period the glass/epoxy specimens had reached a moisture equilibrium condition while glass/linseed oil specimens continued absorbing water. The moisture uptake at the end of the test period was 2.09% for

glass/epoxy specimens (in accordance with the values given by Thomason [7]) and 3.68% for glass/linseed oil specimens.

It can be seen that glass/epoxy specimens show more scatter at the beginning of the water uptake but the scatter stays consistent throughout the testing period. Glass/linseed specimens, however, show less scatter in the first 6 weeks of the testing period and then the scatter starts increasing. This can be attributed to blisters that started to form inside the glass/linseed oil specimens after 6 weeks of immersion. Blisters formed in these specimens on an irregular basis and therefore are a likely cause in the variability in weight gain.

The greater water absorption of glass/linseed oil specimens can be explained by a combination of the blistering and a lower fibre volume fraction. As the matrix is the main component absorbing water in a composite (glass fibres are assumed not to absorb water), a lower fibre volume fraction leads to greater water absorption.

Fig. 1. Moisture uptake curve for glass/epoxy and glass/linseed oil specimens

3.2 Flexural Properties

Figure 2 shows the reduction in flexural strength of glass/epoxy and glass/linseed oil specimens after 10 weeks of immersion. The flexural strength of glass/epoxy specimens reduced by 54% and glass/linseed oil specimens by 71%. However, Figure 3 demonstrates that after an initial rapid reduction in properties, the flexural strength of glass/linseed oil specimens remained the same. On the other hand, the flexural strength of glass/epoxy specimens continued decreasing steadily and had not reached a steady state value after 10 weeks of immersion. This indicates that the properties may drop even further after the test period considered here.

From Figure 3, it can be seen that the flexural strength of glass/linseed oil specimens reduced most rapidly during the first 2 weeks of immersion. In order to understand this drastic reduction in properties, additional flexural testing was carried out after 3 and 6 days of immersion. Figure 4 shows that the flexural strength of glass/linseed oil specimens reduced 32% after 3 days and by 49% of the original properties after 6 days. The degradation of mechanical properties during the first few days of immersion is most likely caused by matrix plasticization as the testing period is too short for extensive chemical reactions to occur. However, Figure 3 indicates that the chemical and physical ageing of glass/linseed oil specimens is rather rapid, occurring during the first 2 weeks of water absorption.

Fig. 2. Reduction in flexural strength in 10 week testing period

Fig. 3. Reduction in flexural strength during a 10 week testing period

Fig. 4. Reduction of flexural strength during the first 2 week immersion period for glass/linseed oil specimens

Despite a greater variability in moisture uptake, the glass/linseed oil specimens showed less variation in flexural test results. This may indicate that the glass/linseed oil specimens have more consistent quality than glass/epoxy specimens which may be due to UV curing that often allows the manufacture of higher quality laminates [13]. However, depending on the cure time, UV curing composites have often poorer mechanical properties and weaker interfaces as the resin may not cure fully [14].

It can be said that the poor performance of glass/linseed oil specimens can be largely attributed to the low fibre volume fraction and matrix failing to transfer the loads to fibres due to weak and vulnerable interface region.

Figure 5 shows the reduction in flexural modulus before ageing and after 10 weeks of immersion. Again, glass/linseed oil specimens show less scatter in the moduli than glass/epoxy specimens. However, the flexural modulus of glass/epoxy specimens seems to be unaffected by moisture absorption. Iglesias *et al.* noticed similar behaviour in their research using the glass/epoxy specimens [8]. It can be noted that the modulus of glass/linseed oil specimens drops down to 51% of the original value after 10 weeks of water absorption. Figure 6 shows that the stress and strain of glass/epoxy specimens both reduced by approximately 50-55% giving no change in the modulus. The strain of glass/linseed oil reduces only slightly while the stress drops remarkably leading to a reduction in flexural modulus. The loss of stiffness may be mainly attributed to the plasticization of the matrix and damaged interface allowing fibres to move more freely inside the matrix, therefore transforming a largely fibre dominated property to a matrix dominated one [15].

Fig. 5.Reduction in flexural modulus in 10 week testing period

Fig. 6.Changes in flexural stress/strain curve after moisture absorption

3.3 Failure Modes

3.3.1 Glass/epoxy

CT scanning was carried out with unaged and aged specimens before and after the flexural failure. Figure 7 shows the failure regions of three 10 weeks aged glass/epoxy specimens and the crack propagation through the specimens. The failure mode of the unaged and the aged glass/epoxy specimens remained the same. Figure 7 shows that the damage occurs mainly as one crack, leading to the failure of the specimens.

Figure 8 demonstrates the tensile failure region of an aged glass/epoxy flexural test specimen. It can be noted that the crack propagates mainly through the fibre bundles, splitting the transverse fibre bundles and breaking the longitudinal fibres. Therefore, it can be concluded that after 10 weeks of water immersion the flexural strength is still mainly fibre dominated.

Fig. 7.Flexural failure of glass/epoxy specimens after 10 weeks of water uptake

Fig. 8. Tensile side of a flexural failure of glass/epoxy specimens after 10 weeks of water uptake

3.3.2 Glass/linseed oil

Figure 9 shows the flexural failure region of unaged glass/linseed oil specimens. From the figure it can be seen that the failure occurs on the compressive and the tensile side of the specimen. Relating this finding to the stress/strain curve in Figure 6, it is believed that the failure of the compressive side of the specimen occurs during the first peak at 1.7% strain because the peak at 1.7% strain could not be due to tensile failure as that would have led to a sudden drop in load in a similar manner to that exhibited by the glass/epoxy specimens. Thus the failure on the tensile side is being represented by the second peak of the curve at 2.5% strain.

Figure 10 shows the tensile failure side of the tested specimen. It can be seen that the crack propagates mainly by breaking the longitudinal fibre bundles. In this image, there is no indication of a crack propagating through transverse fibre bundles as was observed in Figure 8.

The failure region of aged glass/linseed oil specimens can be seen in Figure 11. The failure mode of glass/linseed oil specimens has noticeably changed after only 3 days of ageing. The failure occurs on the compressive side of the specimen. By that point the matrix has already remarkably plasticized and failure of some of the specimens cannot be identified from the produced CT scans. Figures 9 and 11 prove that the failure mode has changed from mainly fibre dominated to a matrix dominated one.

As a result it can be said that the failure of glass/epoxy specimens occurs only on the tensile side even after 10 weeks of ageing and is being represented by mainly one crack. At the same time, the flexural failure mode of glass/linseed oil specimens changes already after 3 days of water absorption from a tensile and fibre dominated property to a compressive and mainly matrix dominated one.

Fig. 9. Flexural failure of glass/linseed oil specimens before ageing

Fig. 10. Tensile side of a flexural failure of glass/linseed oil specimens before ageing

Fig. 11. Flexural failure of glass/linseed oil specimens after 3 days of water uptake

4 Conclusions

From the presented work the following conclusions can be made:

- After 18 weeks of moisture absorption the glass/epoxy specimens reached a moisture equilibrium condition. Glass/linseed oil specimens showed a greater water uptake and this can be attributed to a combination of internal blistering and a lower fibre volume fraction.
- The flexural strength of glass/linseed oil specimens reduced significantly (71%) during the first 2 weeks of immersion. After that period the strength and modulus do not

reduce any further, indicating matrix plasticization and interface damage during these first 2 weeks. The flexural strength of glass/epoxy specimens reduces constantly throughout the testing period indicating a further decrease after the test period. The flexural modulus of glass/epoxy specimens seems to be unaffected by moisture absorption.

- The flexural failure mode of glass/linseed oil specimens changes after 3 days of immersion from a tensile and fibre dominated failure mode into a compressive and matrix dominated one while the failure mode of glass/epoxy specimens remains unchanged.

Future Work

The future work of this research includes investigating the changes of the failure modes in more detail with the aid of Scanning Electron Microscopy and Computed Tomography. In addition, the effect of the fibre volume fraction on the performance of glass/linseed oil specimens will be investigated.

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